

Exploration of Neutrosophic b -semi-open and b -semi-closed Sets

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Abstract. In this write-up, we introduce and develop the concepts of neutrosophic b -semi-open sets and neutrosophic b -semi-closed sets, examining their properties and behaviours under various topological operations. Additionally, we explore their interactions with other established classes of open sets within neutrosophic topological spaces. The notions of neutrosophic b -semi-interior and neutrosophic b -semi-closure are also presented, and their numerous properties are thoroughly investigated.

Keywords: Neutrosophic b -semi-open set ; Neutrosophic b -semi-closed set ; Neutrosophic b -semi-interior ; Neutrosophic b -semi-closure.)

1. Introduction

The term “fuzzy set” was coined by L.A. Zadeh [25] in 1965, and a more generalized version known as the intuitionistic fuzzy set was introduced by K. Atanassov [1] in 1986. Following these developments, Florentin Smarandache [18, 19] further extended the concept, giving rise to the neutrosophic set. A neutrosophic set is characterized by three membership functions: truth-membership, falsity-membership, and indeterminacy-membership functions. Notably, all three neutrosophic components remain unbiased to one another. The introduction of neutrosophy sparked global interest, leading researchers [20–22, 24] to contribute significantly to its advancement. Neutrosophic theory offers a more general and suitable approach to addressing real-life problems. Numerous practical-based works [2, 7, 9] have been carried out in a neutrosophic environment.

In 2012, Salama & Alblowi [22] proposed the concept of a neutrosophic topological space, a generalization of intuitionistic fuzzy topological space developed by D.Coker [4] in 1997. Subsequently, various concepts related to neutrosophic topological spaces were developed by

different researchers [6, 12, 16, 17, 21, 23]. These included the introduction of various types of open and closed sets [3, 5, 10, 11, 13–15] connected to neutrosophic topological spaces.

In 2018, Ebenanjar *et al.* [8], described the concept of neutrosophic b -open sets and investigated some properties. In this article, we present a new type of open set called neutrosophic b -semi-open set and examine some of its fundamental properties. Additionally, we define and study neutrosophic b -semi-interior and neutrosophic b -semi-closure of a neutrosophic set, exploring some properties associated with these concepts.

2. Preliminaries

2.1. Definition: [18]

Let X be the universe of discourse. A neutrosophic set A over X is defined as $A = \{\langle x, \mathcal{T}_A(x), \mathcal{I}_A(x), \mathcal{F}_A(x) \rangle : x \in X\}$, where the functions $\mathcal{T}_A, \mathcal{I}_A, \mathcal{F}_A$ are real standard or non-standard subsets of $]^{-0}, 1^+[$, i.e., $\mathcal{T}_A : X \rightarrow]^{-0}, 1^+[$, $\mathcal{I}_A : X \rightarrow]^{-0}, 1^+[$, $\mathcal{F}_A : X \rightarrow]^{-0}, 1^+[$ and $-0 \leq \mathcal{T}_A(x) + \mathcal{I}_A(x) + \mathcal{F}_A(x) \leq 3^+$.

The neutrosophic set A is characterized by the truth-membership function \mathcal{T}_A , indeterminacy-membership function \mathcal{I}_A , falsity-membership function \mathcal{F}_A .

2.2. Definition: [24]

Let X be the universe of discourse. A single-valued neutrosophic set A over X is defined as $A = \{\langle x, \mathcal{T}_A(x), \mathcal{I}_A(x), \mathcal{F}_A(x) \rangle : x \in X\}$, where $\mathcal{T}_A, \mathcal{I}_A, \mathcal{F}_A$ are functions from X to $[0, 1]$ and $0 \leq \mathcal{T}_A(x) + \mathcal{I}_A(x) + \mathcal{F}_A(x) \leq 3$.

The set of all single valued neutrosophic sets over X is denoted by $\mathcal{N}(X)$.

Throughout this article, a neutrosophic set (NS, for short) will mean a single valued neutrosophic set.

2.3. Definition: [12]

Let $A, B \in \mathcal{N}(X)$. Then

- (i) (Inclusion): If $\mathcal{T}_A(x) \leq \mathcal{T}_B(x), \mathcal{I}_A(x) \geq \mathcal{I}_B(x), \mathcal{F}_A(x) \geq \mathcal{F}_B(x)$ for all $x \in X$ then A is said to be a neutrosophic subset of B and which is denoted by $A \subseteq B$.
- (ii) (Equality): If $A \subseteq B$ and $B \subseteq A$ then $A = B$.
- (iii) (Intersection): The intersection of A and B , denoted by $A \cap B$, is defined as $A \cap B = \{\langle x, \mathcal{T}_A(x) \wedge \mathcal{T}_B(x), \mathcal{I}_A(x) \vee \mathcal{I}_B(x), \mathcal{F}_A(x) \vee \mathcal{F}_B(x) \rangle : x \in X\}$.
- (iv) (Union): The union of A and B , denoted by $A \cup B$, is defined as $A \cup B = \{\langle x, \mathcal{T}_A(x) \vee \mathcal{T}_B(x), \mathcal{I}_A(x) \wedge \mathcal{I}_B(x), \mathcal{F}_A(x) \wedge \mathcal{F}_B(x) \rangle : x \in X\}$.
- (v) (Complement): The complement of the NS A , denoted by A^c , is defined as $A^c = \{\langle x, \mathcal{F}_A(x), 1 - \mathcal{I}_A(x), \mathcal{T}_A(x) \rangle : x \in X\}$

- (vi) (Universal Set): If $\mathcal{T}_A(x) = 1, \mathcal{I}_A(x) = 0, \mathcal{F}_A(x) = 0$ for all $x \in X$ then A is said to be neutrosophic universal set and which is denoted by \tilde{X} .
- (vii) (Empty Set): If $\mathcal{T}_A(x) = 0, \mathcal{I}_A(x) = 1, \mathcal{F}_A(x) = 1$ for all $x \in X$ then A is said to be neutrosophic empty set and which is denoted by $\tilde{\emptyset}$.

2.4. Definition: [22]

Let $\{A_i : i \in \Delta\} \subseteq \mathcal{N}(X)$, where Δ is an index set. Then

- (i) $\cup_{i \in \Delta} A_i = \{\langle x, \vee_{i \in \Delta} \mathcal{T}_{A_i}(x), \wedge_{i \in \Delta} \mathcal{I}_{A_i}(x), \wedge_{i \in \Delta} \mathcal{F}_{A_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X\}$.
- (ii) $\cap_{i \in \Delta} A_i = \{\langle x, \wedge_{i \in \Delta} \mathcal{T}_{A_i}(x), \vee_{i \in \Delta} \mathcal{I}_{A_i}(x), \vee_{i \in \Delta} \mathcal{F}_{A_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X\}$.

2.5. Definition: [12]

Let $\tau \subseteq \mathcal{N}(X)$. Then τ is called a neutrosophic topology on X if

- (i) $\tilde{\emptyset}$ and \tilde{X} belong to τ .
- (ii) Arbitrary union of neutrosophic sets in τ is in τ .
- (iii) Intersection of any two neutrosophic sets in τ is in τ .

If τ is a neutrosophic topology on X then the pair (X, τ) is called a neutrosophic topological space (NTS, for short) over X . The members of τ are called neutrosophic τ -open sets (or neutrosophic open sets or open sets, for short) in X . If for a neutrosophic set A , $A^c \in \tau$ then A is said to be a neutrosophic τ -closed set (or neutrosophic closed set or closed set, for short) in X .

2.6. Definition: [12]

Let (X, τ) be a NTS and $A \in \mathcal{N}(X)$. Then the neutrosophic

- (i) interior of A , denoted by $int(A)$, is defined as $int(A) = \cup\{G : G \in \tau \text{ and } G \subseteq A\}$.
- (ii) closure of A , denoted by $cl(A)$, is defined as $cl(A) = \cap\{G : G \text{ is a neutrosophic closed set and } G \supseteq A\}$.

2.7. Definition: [12]

Let (X, τ) be a NTS and $A, B \in \mathcal{N}(X)$. Then

- (i) $[cl(A)]^c = int(A^c)$
- (ii) $[cl(A)]^c = int(A^c)$
- (iii) $cl(A \cup B) = cl(A) \cup cl(B)$
- (iv) $cl(A \cap B) \subseteq cl(A) \cap cl(B)$
- (v) $int(A \cup B) \supseteq int(A) \cup int(B)$
- (vi) $int(A \cap B) = int(A) \cap int(B)$

2.8. Definition: [8]

Let (X, τ) be a NTS and G be a NS over X . Then G is called a

- (i) neutrosophic b -open (NBO, for short) set iff $G \subseteq [int(cl(G))] \cup [cl(int(G))]$.
- (ii) neutrosophic b -closed (NBC, for short) set iff $G \supseteq [int(cl(G))] \cap [cl(int(G))]$.

2.9. Theorem: [8]

Let (X, τ) be an NTS and G be a NS over X . Then

- (i) G is an NBO set iff G^c is an NBC set.
- (ii) G is an NBC set iff G^c is an NBO set.

2.10. Definition: [8]

Let (X, τ) be an NTS and $A \in \mathcal{N}(X)$. Then the neutrosophic

- (i) b -interior of A , denoted by $bint(A)$, is defined as $bint(A) = \cup\{G : G \text{ is an NBO set in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A\}$.
- (ii) b -closure of A , denoted by $bcl(A)$, is defined as $bcl(A) = \cap\{G : G \text{ is an NBC set in } X \text{ and } G \supseteq A\}$.

2.11. Definition: [10]

Let (X, τ) and (Y, σ) be two NTSs and $A \in \tau$, $B \in \sigma$. Then (X, τ) is called neutrosophic product related to (Y, σ) if for any NSs $C \in \mathcal{N}(X)$ and $D \in \mathcal{N}(Y)$ whenever $C \not\subseteq A^c$ and $D \not\subseteq B^c \Rightarrow C \times D \subseteq A^c \times \tilde{Y} \cup \tilde{X} \times B^c$, there exist $A_1 \in \tau$, $B_1 \in \sigma$ such that $C \subseteq A_1^c$ or $D \subseteq B_1^c$ and $A_1^c \times \tilde{Y} \cup \tilde{X} \times B_1^c = A^c \times \tilde{Y} \cup \tilde{X} \times B^c$.

2.12. Definition: [10]

Let (X, τ) and (Y, σ) be two NTSs such that X is neutrosophic product related to Y . Then for the NSs $A \in \mathcal{N}(X)$ and $B \in \mathcal{N}(Y)$, we have

- (i) $cl(A \times B) = cl(A) \times cl(B)$.
- (ii) $int(A \times B) = int(A) \times int(B)$.

3. Main Results**3.1. Definition:**

Let (X, τ) be an NTS. A non-empty NS $A \in \mathcal{N}(X)$ is called a

- (i) neutrosophic b -semi-open set (NBSO set, for short) in X iff there exists an NBO set G in X such that $G \subseteq A \subseteq cl(G)$.
- (ii) neutrosophic b -semi-closed set (NBSC set, for short) in X iff there exists an NBC set G in X such that $int(G) \subseteq A \subseteq G$.

The collection of all the neutrosophic b -semi-open sets of the NTS (X, τ) will be denoted by $NBSO(X)$.

3.2. Example:

Let $X = \{a, b\}$, $\tau = \{\emptyset, \tilde{X}\}$. Obviously (X, τ) is an NTS. Let us consider the NSs $A = \{\langle a, 0.9, 0, 0 \rangle, \langle b, 0, 1, 1 \rangle\}$, $B = \{\langle a, 1, 0, 0 \rangle, \langle b, 0.7, 0.6, 0.4 \rangle\}$, $C = \{\langle a, 0, 1, 1 \rangle, \langle b, 0.4, 0.4, 0.7 \rangle\}$ and $D = \{\langle a, 0, 1, 0.9 \rangle, \langle b, 1, 0, 0 \rangle\}$ over X . Now $cl(A) = \tilde{X} \Rightarrow int(cl(A)) = \tilde{X}$ which gives $A \subseteq int(cl(A))$, i.e. $A \subseteq int(cl(A)) \cup cl(int(A))$. Therefore A is an NBO set. Clearly $A \subseteq B \subseteq cl(A)$. Therefore B is an NBSO set in X . Clearly D is an NBC set as $A^c = D$. Now $int(D) = \tilde{\emptyset}$ and $C \subseteq D$. Therefore $int(D) \subseteq C \subseteq D$ and so, C is an NBSC set in X .

3.3. Proposition:

- (i) Every NBO set in an NTS is an NBSO set.
- (ii) Every NBC set in an NTS is an NBSC set.

Proof: (i) Let (X, τ) be an NTS and A be an NBO set in X . Since $A \subseteq A \subseteq cl(A)$. Therefore A is an NBSO set.

(ii) Let (X, τ) be an NTS and A be an NBC set in X . Then A^c is an NBO set and so, A^c is an NBSO set [by (i)]. Therefore, there exists an NBO set B such that $B \subseteq A^c \subseteq cl(B) \Rightarrow [cl(B)]^c \subseteq A \subseteq B^c \Rightarrow int(B^c) \subseteq A \subseteq B^c \Rightarrow A$ is an NBSC set as B^c is an NBC set.

3.4. Proposition:

- (i) Every neutrosophic open set in an NTS is an NBSO set.
- (ii) Every neutrosophic closed set in an NTS is an NBSC set.

Proof: (i) Let (X, τ) be an NTS and $A \in \tau$. Then $A = int(A)$. Now $A \subseteq cl(A) \Rightarrow int(A) \subseteq int(cl(A)) \Rightarrow A \subseteq int(cl(A)) \Rightarrow A \subseteq int(cl(A)) \cup cl(int(A)) \Rightarrow A$ is an NBO set. Thus for $A \in \tau$, there exists an NBO set A such that $A \subseteq A \subseteq cl(A)$. Therefore A is an NBSO set. Hence proved.

(ii) Let (X, τ) be an NTS and A be a neutrosophic closed set. Then A^c is a neutrosophic open set and so, A^c is an NBSO set [by (i)]. Then there exists an NBO set B such that $B \subseteq A^c \subseteq cl(B) \Rightarrow [cl(B)]^c \subseteq A \subseteq B^c \Rightarrow int(B^c) \subseteq A \subseteq B^c \Rightarrow A$ is an NBSC set as B^c is an NBC set. Hence proved.

3.5. Remark:

Converses of the propositions 3.4(i) and 3.4(ii) are not true. We establish by the following example.

Let $X = \{a, b\}$, $\tau = \{\tilde{\emptyset}, \tilde{X}\}$. Obviously (X, τ) is an NTS. Let us consider the NSs $A = \{\langle a, 1, 0, 0 \rangle, \langle b, 0, 1, 1 \rangle\}$ and $B = \{\langle a, 0, 1, 1 \rangle, \langle b, 1, 0, 0 \rangle\}$ over X . Now $int(cl(A)) = int(\tilde{X}) = \tilde{X}$ which gives $A \subseteq int(cl(A))$, i.e. $A \subseteq int(cl(A)) \cup cl(int(A))$. Therefore A is an NBO set and so by 3.3(i), A is an NBSO set. Clearly A is not a neutrosophic open set. Thus an NBSO set may not be a neutrosophic open set.

Again B is not a neutrosophic closed set as $B^c = A$ is not a neutrosophic open set. As A is an NBO set, so by 2.9, $A^c = B$ is an NBC set and therefore by 3.3(ii), B is an NBSC set. Thus an NBSC set may not be a neutrosophic closed set.

3.6. Proposition:

Let (X, τ) be an NTS and $G \in \mathcal{N}(X)$. Then G is an NBSO set iff G^c is an NBSC set.

Proof: Necessary part: G is an NBSO set \Rightarrow there exists an NBO set H such that $H \subseteq G \subseteq cl(H) \Rightarrow [cl(H)]^c \subseteq G^c \subseteq H^c \Rightarrow int(H^c) \subseteq G^c \subseteq H^c \Rightarrow G^c$ is an NBSC set as H^c is an NBC set.

Sufficient part: G^c is an NBSC set \Rightarrow there exists an NBC set H such that $int(H) \subseteq G^c \subseteq H \Rightarrow H^c \subseteq G \subseteq [int(H)]^c \Rightarrow H^c \subseteq G \subseteq cl(H^c) \Rightarrow G$ is an NBSO set as H^c is an NBO set.

3.7. Proposition:

In an NTS, union of an arbitrary collection of NBSO sets is an NBSO set.

Proof: Let (X, τ) be an NTS and $\{G_\lambda : \lambda \in \Delta\}$ be an arbitrary collection of NBSO sets in X , where Δ is an index set. Since G_λ is an NBSO set, so there exists an NBO set H_λ for each G_λ , $\lambda \in \Delta$ such that $H_\lambda \subseteq G_\lambda \subseteq cl(H_\lambda)$. Now $H_\lambda \subseteq G_\lambda \subseteq cl(H_\lambda)$ for each $\lambda \in \Delta \Rightarrow \cup_{\lambda \in \Delta} H_\lambda \subseteq \cup_{\lambda \in \Delta} G_\lambda \subseteq \cup_{\lambda \in \Delta} cl(H_\lambda) \Rightarrow \cup_{\lambda \in \Delta} H_\lambda \subseteq \cup_{\lambda \in \Delta} G_\lambda \subseteq cl(\cup_{\lambda \in \Delta} H_\lambda)$. Since arbitrary union of NBO sets is an NBO set, so $\cup_{\lambda \in \Delta} H_\lambda$ is an NBO set. Thus there exists an NBO set $\cup_{\lambda \in \Delta} H_\lambda$ such that $\cup_{\lambda \in \Delta} H_\lambda \subseteq \cup_{\lambda \in \Delta} G_\lambda \subseteq cl(\cup_{\lambda \in \Delta} H_\lambda)$. Therefore $\cup_{\lambda \in \Delta} G_\lambda$ is an NBSO set. Hence proved.

3.8. Proposition:

- (i) In an NTS, union of a neutrosophic open set and an NBSO set is an NBSO set.
- (ii) In an NTS, union of an NBO set and an NBSO set is an NBSO set.

Proof: Very obvious.

3.9. Proposition:

In an NTS, intersection of an arbitrary collection of NBSC sets is an NBSC set.

Proof: Let (X, τ) be an NTS and $\{G_\lambda : \lambda \in \Delta\}$ be an arbitrary collection of NBSC sets in X , where Δ is an index set. Then G_λ^c is an NBSO set for each $\lambda \in \Delta \Rightarrow \cup_{\lambda \in \Delta} G_\lambda^c$ is an NBSO set [by 3.7] $\Rightarrow (\cap_{\lambda \in \Delta} G_\lambda)^c$ is an NBSO set $\Rightarrow \cap_{\lambda \in \Delta} G_\lambda$ is an NBSC set [by 3.6]. Hence proved.

3.10. Proposition:

- (i) In an NTS, intersection of a neutrosophic closed set and an NBSC set is an NBSC set.
- (ii) In an NTS, intersection of an NBC set and an NBSC set is an NBSC set.

Proof: Very obvious.

3.11. Proposition:

Let (X, τ) be an NTS and $G \in \mathcal{N}(X)$. Then G is an NBSO set iff $G \subseteq cl(bint(G))$.

Proof: Necessary part: Since G is an NBSO set, so there exists an NBO set H such that $H \subseteq G \subseteq cl(H)$. Obviously $H \subseteq bint(G)$ which implies $cl(H) \subseteq cl(bint(G))$. Therefore $G \subseteq cl(bint(G))$.

Sufficient part: Given $G \subseteq cl(bint(G))$. Since $bint(G) \subseteq G$, so $bint(G) \subseteq G \subseteq cl(bint(G))$. As $bint(G)$ is an NBO set, so G is an NBSO set.

3.12. Proposition:

Let (X, τ) be an NTS and $G \in \mathcal{N}(X)$. Then G is an NBSC set iff $G \supseteq int(bcl(G))$.

Proof: G is an NBSC set $\Leftrightarrow G^c$ is an NBSO set $\Leftrightarrow G^c \subseteq cl(bint(G^c))$ [by 3.11] $\Leftrightarrow G^c \subseteq cl[(bcl(G))^c] \Leftrightarrow G^c \subseteq [int(bcl(A))]^c \Leftrightarrow G \supseteq int(bcl(A))$.

3.13. Proposition:

Let G be an NBSO set in an NTS (X, τ) . If $K \in \mathcal{N}(X)$ is such that $bint(G) \subseteq K \subseteq bcl(G)$ then K is an NBSO set in X .

Proof: Since G is an NBSO set, so there exists an NBO set H such that $H \subseteq G \subseteq cl(H)$. Obviously $H \subseteq bint(G) \subseteq G \subseteq bcl(G)$. Again $G \subseteq cl(H) \Rightarrow bcl(G) \subseteq bcl(cl(H)) \subseteq cl(cl(H)) = cl(H)$. Thus, $H \subseteq bint(G) \subseteq K \subseteq bcl(G) \subseteq cl(H)$. Therefore, $H \subseteq K \subseteq cl(H)$, which ensures that K is an NBSO set in X .

3.14. Proposition:

Let G be an NBSC set in an NTS (X, τ) . If $K \in \mathcal{N}(X)$ is such that $bint(G) \subseteq K \subseteq bcl(G)$ then K is an NBSC set in X .

Proof: G is an NBSC set $\Leftrightarrow G^c$ is an NBSO set. Now $bint(G) \subseteq K \subseteq bcl(G) \Leftrightarrow [bint(G)]^c \supseteq K^c \supseteq [bcl(G)]^c \Leftrightarrow bint(G^c) \subseteq K^c \subseteq bcl(G^c) \Leftrightarrow K^c$ is an NBSO set [by 3.13] $\Leftrightarrow K$ is an NBSC set in X .

3.15. Definition:

Let (X, τ) be an NTS and $A \in \mathcal{N}(X)$. Then the neutrosophic b -semi-interior of A , denoted by $NBSint(A)$, is defined as $NBSint(A) = \cup\{G : G \text{ is an NBSO set in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A\}$.

3.16. Proposition:

Let (X, τ) be an NTS and $A, B \in \mathcal{N}(X)$. Then the following hold.

- (i) $NBSint(A)$ is an NBSO set.
- (ii) $NBSint(A) \subseteq A$
- (iii) A is an NBSO set iff $A = NBSint(A)$.
- (iv) $NBSint(\tilde{\emptyset}) = \tilde{\emptyset}$
- (v) $NBSint(\tilde{X}) = \tilde{X}$
- (vi) $NBSint(NBSint(A)) = NBSint(A)$

Proof:

- (i) Since $NBSint(A)$ is the union of NBSO sets, so by 3.7, $NBSint(A)$ is an NBSO set.
- (ii) Since $NBSint(A)$ is the union of all NBSO sets contained in A , so $NBSint(A) \subseteq A$.
- (iii) Suppose that A is an NBSO set. Since $A \subseteq A$ and A is an NBSO set, so $A \subseteq NBSint(A)$. Again $NBSint(A) \subseteq A$ [by (ii)]. Therefore $A = NBSint(A)$. Conversely if $A = NBSint(A)$ then A is an NBSO set as $NBSint(A)$ is NBSO set [by (i)]. Hence proved.
- (iv) Since every neutrosophic open set is an NBSO set, so $\tilde{\emptyset}$ is an NBSO set and therefore by (iii), $NBSint(\tilde{\emptyset}) = \tilde{\emptyset}$.
- (v) Since every neutrosophic open set is an NBSO set, so \tilde{X} is an NBSO set and therefore by (iii), $NBSint(\tilde{X}) = \tilde{X}$.
- (vi) Since by (i), $NBSint(A)$ is an NBSO set, so by (iii), $NBSint(NBSint(A)) = NBSint(A)$.

3.17. Proposition:

Let (X, τ) be an NTS and $A, B \in \mathcal{N}(X)$. Then the following hold.

- (i) $A \subseteq B \Rightarrow NBSint(A) \subseteq NBSint(B)$
- (ii) $NBSint(A \cup B) \supseteq NBSint(A) \cup NBSint(B)$.
- (iii) $NBSint(A \cap B) \subseteq NBSint(A) \cap NBSint(B)$.

Proof:

- (i) Since $A \subseteq B$ and $NBSint(A) \subseteq A$, so $NBSint(A) \subseteq B$. Since $NBSint(A)$ is an NBSO set such that $NBSint(A) \subseteq B$ and since $NBSint(B)$ is the largest NBSO set contained in B , so $NBSint(A) \subseteq NBSint(B)$.

(ii) $A \subseteq A \cup B \Rightarrow NBSint(A) \subseteq NBSint(A \cup B)$. Similarly $NBSint(B) \subseteq NBSint(A \cup B)$. Therefore $NBSint(A \cup B) \supseteq NBSint(A) \cup NBSint(B)$.

(iii) $A \cap B \subseteq A \Rightarrow NBSint(A \cap B) \subseteq NBSint(A)$. Similarly $NBSint(A \cap B) \subseteq NBSint(B)$. Therefore $NBSint(A \cap B) \subseteq NBSint(A) \cap NBSint(B)$.

3.18. Definition:

Let (X, τ) be an NTS and $A \in \mathcal{N}(X)$. Then the neutrosophic b -semi-closure of A , denoted by $NBScl(A)$, is defined as $NBScl(A) = \cap \{G : G \text{ is an NBSC set in } X \text{ and } G \supseteq A\}$.

3.19. Proposition:

Let (X, τ) be an NTS and $A \in \mathcal{N}(X)$. Then the following hold.

- (i) $NBScl(A)$ is an NBSC set.
- (ii) $A \subseteq NBScl(A)$.
- (iii) A is an NBSC set iff $A = NBScl(A)$.
- (iv) $NBScl(\tilde{\emptyset}) = \tilde{\emptyset}$
- (v) $NBScl(\tilde{X}) = \tilde{X}$
- (vi) $NBScl(NBScl(A)) = NBScl(A)$

Proof:

- (i) As $NBScl(A)$ is the intersection of NBSC sets, so by 3.9, $NBScl(A)$ is an NBSC set.
- (ii) As $NBScl(A)$ is the intersection of all NBSC sets containing A , so $A \subseteq NBScl(A)$.
- (iii) Suppose that A is an NBSC set. Since $A \supseteq A$ and A is an NBSC set, so $NBScl(A) \subseteq A$. Again $A \subseteq NBScl(A)$ [by (ii)]. Therefore $A = NBScl(A)$. Conversely if $A = NBScl(A)$ then A is an NBSC set as $NBScl(A)$ is an NBSC set [by (i)]. Hence proved.
- (iv) Since every neutrosophic closed set is an NBSC set, so $\tilde{\emptyset}$ is an NBSC set and therefore by (iii), $NBScl(\tilde{\emptyset}) = \tilde{\emptyset}$.
- (v) Since every neutrosophic closed set is an NBSC set, so \tilde{X} is an NBSC set and therefore by (iii), $NBScl(\tilde{X}) = \tilde{X}$.
- (vi) Since by (i), $NBScl(A)$ is an NBSC set, so by (iii), $NBScl(NBScl(A)) = NBScl(A)$.

3.20. Proposition:

Let (X, τ) be an NTS and $A, B \in \mathcal{N}(X)$. Then the following hold.

- (i) $A \subseteq B \Rightarrow NBScl(A) \subseteq NBScl(B)$
- (ii) $NBScl(A \cup B) \supseteq NBScl(A) \cup NBScl(B)$.
- (iii) $NBScl(A \cap B) \subseteq NBScl(A) \cap NBScl(B)$.

Proof:

(i) $A \subseteq B$ and $B \subseteq NBScl(B)$, so $A \subseteq NBScl(B)$. Since $NBScl(B)$ is an NBSC set such that $A \subseteq NBScl(B)$, so $NBScl(A) \subseteq NBScl(B)$.

(ii) $A \subseteq A \cup B \Rightarrow NBScl(A) \subseteq NBScl(A \cup B)$. Similarly $NBScl(B) \subseteq NBScl(A \cup B)$. Therefore $NBScl(A \cup B) \supseteq NBScl(A) \cup NBScl(B)$.

(iii) $A \cap B \subseteq A \Rightarrow NBScl(A \cap B) \subseteq NBScl(A)$. Similarly $NBScl(A \cap B) \subseteq NBScl(B)$. Therefore $NBScl(A \cap B) \subseteq NBScl(A) \cap NBScl(B)$.

3.21. Proposition:

Let (X, τ) be an NTS and $A, B \in \mathcal{N}(X)$. Then the following hold.

$$(i) [NBScl(A)]^c = NBSint(A^c)$$

$$(ii) NBScl(A^c) = [NBSint(A)]^c.$$

Proof: (i) We have $NBScl(A) = \cap\{G : G \text{ is an NBSC set in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq G\} \Rightarrow [NBScl(A)]^c = [\cap\{G : G \text{ is an NBSC set in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq G\}]^c \Rightarrow [NBScl(A)]^c = \cup\{G^c : G^c \text{ is an NBSO set in } X \text{ and } G^c \subseteq A^c\} \Rightarrow [NBScl(A)]^c = NBSint(A^c)$.

(ii) Replacing A by A^c in (i), we get $[NBScl(A^c)]^c = NBSint((A^c)^c) \Rightarrow [NBScl(A^c)]^c = NBSint(A) \Rightarrow NBScl(A^c) = [NBSint(A)]^c$.

3.22. Remark:

If (X, τ) is an NTS and $G \in \mathcal{N}(X)$ then it is very evident from above that $int(G) \subseteq bint(G) \subseteq NBSint(G) \subseteq G \subseteq NBScl(G) \subseteq bcl(G) \subseteq cl(G)$.

3.23. Proposition:

Let (X, τ) and (Y, σ) be two NTSs such that X is product related to Y . If A is an NBO set in X and B is an NBO set in Y then the product $A \times B$ is an NBO set in the product space $X \times Y$.

Proof: As A and B are NBO sets, so $A \subseteq [int(cl(A))] \cup [cl(int(A))]$ and $B \subseteq [int(cl(B))] \cup [cl(int(B))]$. Then $A \times B \subseteq [int(cl(A)) \cup cl(int(A))] \times [int(cl(B)) \cup cl(int(B))] = [(int(cl(A))) \times (int(cl(B)))] \cup [(cl(int(A))) \times (cl(int(B)))] = int[cl(A) \times cl(B)] \cup cl[int(A) \times int(B)]$ [by 2.12] = $int[cl(A \times B)] \cup cl[int(A \times B)]$ [by 2.12]. Therefore, $A \times B \subseteq [int(cl(A \times B))] \cup [cl(int(A \times B))]$ and so, $A \times B$ is an NBO set in the product space $X \times Y$.

3.24. Proposition:

Let (X, τ) and (Y, σ) be two NTSs such that X is product related to Y . If A is an NBSO set in X and B is an NBSO set in Y then the product $A \times B$ is an NBSO set in the product space $X \times Y$.

Proof: As A is an NBSO set, so there exists an NBO set G such that $G \subseteq A \subseteq cl(G)$. Similarly $H \subseteq B \subseteq cl(H)$ for some NBO set H in X . Then $G \times H \subseteq A \times B \subseteq cl(G) \times cl(H) \Rightarrow G \times H \subseteq A \times B \subseteq cl(G \times H)$ [by 2.12]. Since by 3.23, $G \times H$ is an NBO set in $X \times Y$, so $A \times B$ is an NBSO set in $X \times Y$.

4. Conclusions

In this article, we have introduced neutrosophic b -semi-open sets and neutrosophic b -semi-closed sets within the framework of neutrosophic topological spaces, exploring their basic properties. We have also defined the neutrosophic b -semi-interior and neutrosophic b -semi-closure of a neutrosophic set, investigating various properties associated with them.

In future work, we plan to explore new concepts involving these structures. We hope that the findings of this article will assist the research community in advancing the development of different aspects of neutrosophic topology

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